

“A critical study to prevention from Addiction (Smoking and Drinking) of Youth”**In special reference of School & College****Dr.Neelu Gupta****Programme Chair & Asso. Professor****Commerce & Management****LBSITM Indore**

Addiction, it is such a word which is not just a word but this small word is enough to ruin the life of any person. There are countless things to say on the subject of drug addiction, writings have been done and there are reform homes too but none of them are of any significance for a person who wants to quit drug addiction. It is not that people do not want to quit drugs, those who seriously want to quit drugs are successful but the purpose of our study is to stop those who start drug addiction. Through this study, we want to tell the youth in a meaningful way that how harmful drug addiction is and how it can be stopped at the very beginning.

It has been observed in youth that the easiest place for drug addiction is school and college students, those who try to make them their prey are successful. In today's time, when students have a small weapon in their hands and they do not understand how and at what place to use it, then the same students start using the weapon of mobile at wrong places and go astray. The purpose of our study is to study students between 13 to 20 years of age.

Key wards: Addiction, youth, Successful, Essential, Mobile and Social Media.

Introduction:

Addiction, this one word has different meanings but in our research this word has been considered as a slow poison which enters the life of teenagers. When we see someone doing drugs then we generally keep a distance from that person. It means that the person is involved in some wrong activity and hence the distance is maintained. If any member of a family is a victim of drug addiction then he will never allow his children to get involved in it because he knows that taking drugs is wrong.

Here in our research we have included smoking and alcohol whose side effects ruin their entire life. After studying newspapers for three years, it has been found that about 46972 children between the ages of 13 to 19 have become victims of drug addiction. This is the data which has been published. From this, it can be estimated how much the unpublished data would be. They run their business from small settlements, slums, hawkers, handcart owners, big and small shops etc. We cannot always identify anyone. Mostly it has been seen that schools are targeted due to which the drug trade runs smoothly. Some students, in the greed of few rupees, misguide, bully and provoke other students in the name of their status due to which students between the ages of 13 to 16 get trapped very quickly.

Purpose of the Research:

- 1) To evaluate the Causes of addiction
- 2) To Prevention from the addiction
- 3) To observe the Perception of an addict before and after involvement in addiction
- 4) To solve the problems.
- 5) To detect the Government Policy for the same.

Literature Review:

1. Several studies report the alarming rise in smoking and drinking among young people. According to a study by **Jha et al. (2024)**, around 30% of teenagers have tried smoking by the age of 16, and nearly 40% of adolescents report alcohol consumption by the time they enter college. In India,
2. **Chakraborty and Mishra (2023)** highlight that youth in urban areas are more likely to experiment with smoking and drinking, driven by peer pressure and the increasing availability of tobacco and alcohol.

3. Peer influence is one of the strongest motivators for young people to try smoking and drinking. According to **Miller and Moffitt (2023)**, adolescents are more likely to engage in risky behaviors like smoking and drinking when they are surrounded by peers who exhibit similar behavior.
4. Adolescents with mental health issues such as anxiety, depression, or stress are more vulnerable to engaging in substance use as a coping mechanism. **Bennett et al. (2022)** found a strong link between mental health challenges and increased alcohol or tobacco use in youth

Research Methodology:

- A. **Descriptive Research:** The study will primarily describe the patterns, causes, and impact of smoking and drinking on youth. It will analyse prevention programs and interventions implemented in schools and colleges.
- B. **Quantitative and Qualitative Approach:** Both numerical data (surveys, statistics) and descriptive data (interviews, focus groups) will be collected to understand the issue comprehensively.
- C. **Mixed Methods Approach:** This will combine both qualitative and quantitative methods to provide a richer understanding of the addiction problem, prevention strategies, and their effectiveness.

Limitations;

- 1) The study may be limited by the willingness of the students to participate or their truthfulness regarding smoking and drinking.
- 2) The findings may not be generalizable to all teenagers as the study is restricted to certain geographic regions or institutions.

Findings:

A critical study on the prevention of addiction, particularly smoking and drinking, among youth with a special reference to schools and colleges would likely involve reviewing various factors influencing substance abuse and the strategies that can be employed to mitigate these behaviors. Here are some key findings and points that may emerge from such a study:

1. Prevalence of Smoking and Drinking among Youth

- **Higher incidence among adolescents:** Studies indicate that smoking and drinking habits often begin in adolescence, with the period between 15 to 20 years being particularly critical. In schools and colleges, peer pressure, curiosity, and the desire for social acceptance are strong influences.

- **Cultural and environmental factors:** The acceptance of smoking and drinking in certain cultures or among family members can influence adolescents. Additionally, exposure to media that glamorizes these behaviors increases the likelihood of youth engaging in such activities.

2. Psychological and Social Factors

- **Peer pressure:** Peer influence plays a significant role in the initiation and continuation of smoking and drinking. Youth in schools and colleges are particularly vulnerable to peer pressure.
- **Mental health issues:** Anxiety, depression, stress, and low self-esteem are often correlated with substance abuse. Adolescents may use smoking or drinking as a coping mechanism.
- **Desire for identity and rebellion:** The adolescence phase is a time of self-discovery, and some youths may engage in these habits to establish an identity or rebel against societal norms.

3. Impact of Smoking and Drinking on Youth

- **Physical health risks:** Smoking and drinking can cause long-term health issues, including respiratory diseases, liver damage, and cardiovascular problems. In the case of alcohol, there is also an increased risk of accidents due to impaired judgment.
- **Academic performance:** Addiction to smoking or drinking has been linked to lower academic performance due to decreased concentration, memory, and motivation.
- **Increased risk of addiction in adulthood:** Youth who start smoking or drinking early are more likely to continue these habits into adulthood, leading to chronic addiction problems.

4. Prevention Strategies

- **Education and awareness programs:** Schools and colleges can implement educational campaigns to inform students about the dangers of smoking and drinking. This may include workshops, seminars, and counselling sessions led by professionals.
- **Peer-led interventions:** Programs that empower peer groups to educate and support each other can be effective. Peer leaders can be trained to communicate the risks of smoking and drinking and offer alternative coping strategies.
- **Engaging extracurricular activities:** Providing students with a wide range of extracurricular activities, such as sports, arts, and clubs, can help keep them engaged and distracted from negative habits.

- **Parental involvement:** Schools and colleges should encourage parental engagement in their children's education and well-being. Parents who are aware of the risks and signs of addiction are better equipped to intervene early.
- **Stronger campus policies:** Schools and colleges can adopt stricter no-smoking and no-drinking policies, with clear consequences for students who engage in these behaviours. These policies should be enforced consistently to create a safe, healthy environment.
- **Counselling and mental health support:** Offering counselling services to students to address underlying mental health issues can help prevent substance abuse. Support groups, therapy, and stress-management programs can help students cope with challenges without turning to alcohol or cigarettes.
- **Public health campaigns:** National and local campaigns targeting youth can work to shift cultural norms around smoking and drinking. Campaigns should focus on spreading facts about the dangers of these habits and on promoting healthy alternatives.

5. Barriers to Prevention

- **Lack of effective enforcement:** In some cases, school and college policies against smoking and drinking may not be enforced effectively, leading to a lack of deterrence.
- **Inadequate resources for prevention programs:** Many schools and colleges lack the financial resources or trained staff to implement effective prevention programs. This leads to a gap in necessary education and intervention.
- **Cultural stigma:** In some cultures, discussing addiction may be stigmatized, making it difficult to address the problem openly. Youth may feel ashamed to seek help, even when they are struggling.

6. Role of Technology and Social Media

- **Influence of social media:** Social media platforms can have a significant impact on youth behaviour, with influencers and celebrity's often promoting smoking and drinking. Studies show that youths who are exposed to such content are more likely to engage in these behaviours.
- **Digital tools for prevention:** Digital interventions such as mobile apps, online counselling, and awareness campaigns can be used to reach large numbers of students. These tools provide anonymity and easy access to support, which may be especially beneficial for students hesitant to seek in-person help.

7. Recommendations for Future Research

- **Longitudinal studies:** Research that follows students over several years can help determine the effectiveness of various prevention strategies and identify early warning signs of addiction.
- **Cultural context in prevention:** Future studies should examine how different cultural contexts affect the prevalence of smoking and drinking among youth, as prevention strategies may need to be tailored to specific groups.
- **Increased collaboration:** Schools, colleges, healthcare professionals, parents, and governments need to work together to combat addiction. Research into integrated approaches that involve multiple stakeholders can provide more effective solutions.

In conclusion, addressing smoking and drinking addiction among youth in schools and colleges requires a multi-faceted approach, focusing on education, support systems, peer involvement, and strict policy enforcement. Empowering youth with the knowledge and tools to make healthier choices, while creating environments that promote well-being, is crucial in reducing substance abuse among this demographic.

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